

**AN ANALYSIS OF MOOD AND MODALITY STRUCTURES
IN PRESIDENT BOLA AHMED TINUBU'S 2024
INDEPENDENCE DAY SPEECH**

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Abstract

The 2024 Independence Day speech by President Bola Ahmed Tinubu represents an important communicative act in Nigeria's political and social discourse. This study aimed to explore the Mood and Modality Structures in President Bola Ahmed Tinubu's Independence Day speech on October, 1st, 2024 and this was achieved by examining the mood structures in President Tinubu's 2024 Independence Day speech; identifying the modality structures in the speech to reflect the President's political stance, authority and engagement with the public; and by exploring how different mood and modality choices of President Tinubu in his 2024 Independence Day's speech work together to create persuasive and authoritative discourse.

The research employed a qualitative approach and ten clauses were purposively selected from the 2024 Nigerian Presidential Independence Day's Speech for analysis. Analysis of the clauses were anchored using the patterns of mood and modality systems in Halliday's Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL). Findings reveal that the President employed declarative moods to assert policies and achievements, imperatives to mobilise citizens and interrogative mood to foster unity. Also, modals were used to express both certainty and possibility. These

helped him to construct a voice that could be perceived as persuasive and inclusive by the common people. Finally, the study concluded that Political actors and their speechwriters should be more deliberate in using mood and modality in their speeches to balance authority with empathy, especially during sensitive national occasions because this can affect their connections and perception by the public.

Keywords: political speech, mood, modality, authority, communicative

1.0 Introduction

The 2024 Independence Day speech by President Bola Ahmed Tinubu represents an important communicative act in Nigeria's political and social discourse. Delivered annually, these speeches offer a moment for the President to reflect on the nation's progress, address pressing issues, and articulate visions for the country's future. From a linguistic perspective, political speeches, especially those delivered on national occasions such as Independence Day, serve as a rich field of study. This is because they encapsulate the interplay of language, power, and ideology, offering insights into the leader's stance on critical matters (Vaezi, 2021).

In his 2024 Independence Day speech, President Bola Ahmed Tinubu addressed the Nigerian nation, marking a significant occasion in the country's history. This speech, delivered on October 1st, 2024, commemorated Nigeria's 64th year of independence and provided a platform for the President to reflect on the country's progress, challenges, and future aspirations. The speech also served as a vital opportunity for President Tinubu to outline his administration's priorities and policies, highlighting areas of economic reform, security improvements, and social development.

The context of the speech can be understood within the broader Nigerian political, social, and cultural landscape. Politically, Nigeria is at a crossroads, with President Tinubu's administration seeking to address longstanding issues such as economic instability, corruption, and security concerns. Socially, the nation is grappling with the effects of inequality, unemployment, and regional disparities that have shaped public sentiment. Culturally, the speech was delivered to a diverse audience, with multiple ethnicities, religions, and cultural traditions

represented across the country. As such, the President's language and tone needed to be inclusive and reflective of the diverse nature of Nigerian society, while also demonstrating a sense of unity and collective purpose (Vaezi, 2021).

Independence Day speeches in Nigeria hold significant importance as they provide a moment of reflection on the nation's achievements and setbacks. These speeches offer political leaders the chance to unify the nation, reinforce national identity, and present visions for the future. The role of political speeches in leadership communication cannot be understated, as they serve not only as formal addresses but also as tools for influencing public opinion and shaping the political discourse. For President Tinubu, his 2024 Independence Day speech was a crucial moment to affirm his leadership and solidify his political authority, while also addressing the concerns of the Nigerian populace and guiding them toward a shared national vision.

In this study, the focus is on the mood and modality structures present in President Tinubu's speech. Mood and modality are two critical linguistic elements that reveal how speakers organise their messages and express attitudes toward reality, commitment, and authority. Mood refers to the grammatical choices speakers make to signal their intention, such as declarative, interrogative, and imperative sentences. Modality, on the other hand, deals with the speaker's expression of possibility, necessity, obligation, and likelihood, often conveyed through auxiliary verbs like *can*, *will*, *may*, or *must*.

From a simple linguistic standpoint, the mood structures in the speech help to establish the tone of the communication. For instance, the President's use of declarative sentences signifies the authoritative stance often assumed by political leaders when delivering speeches. It reflects the certainty and assertiveness that leaders wish to project, especially on a significant occasion like Independence Day. Conversely, according to Chinyere and Bibian (2023), modality introduces nuance into the speech, revealing not just the President's direct statements but also the degree of confidence or obligation tied to certain promises or projections. Modal verbs and expressions indicate how the President navigates his commitments to the Nigerian people, showing areas where he is more certain of the future or where he acknowledges challenges.

On a more complex level, understanding mood and modality structures allows us to assess the ideological implications embedded within the speech. Political leaders often use modality to indicate the levels of commitment or intention they have to their policy goals, which can influence public perception and reaction (Derin et al., 2020). The choice of modal verbs such as will or must might suggest a firm determination to implement certain reforms, while verbs like may or could could signal openness or uncertainty. These linguistic choices are critical in understanding how President Tinubu communicates his political vision, his leadership approach, and his responsiveness to the needs and concerns of the Nigerian populace (Aro, 2023).

As stated by Anagbogu, Mba, and Eme (2010), language serves as a tool that humans have developed to express ideas, emotions, desires, and more, through intricate vocal or written symbols. Additionally, Umera-okeke (2009) defines language as a set of symbols used by a specific group to communicate among themselves, both verbally and in writing. Without language, communication between individuals would be difficult, and without effective use of language, intended messages would fail to reach an audience. Therefore, it is essential to recognize that a good speech must be clear and unambiguous. Given the importance of communication and the role of setting agendas in political leadership, it is crucial to analyze language use in Nigeria's Inaugural Day speeches, typically delivered on Nigeria's Democracy Day in an election year, and Independence Day speeches, typically given on October 1st. Such analysis can reveal the discourses used and other valuable insights. Various studies have explored media coverage of political speeches and their relevance to audiences, including works by Nwoye (2017).

Moreover, analyzing the mood and modality structures offers insights into the broader political and social dynamics of Nigeria at the time. By examining how the President expresses obligation, possibility, or certainty, we can better understand how language is employed not just for communication, but for shaping public opinion, rallying support, and asserting authority. This analysis is especially pertinent given the challenges Nigeria faces, including economic instability, security concerns, and political fragmentation. The ways in which the

President frames these issues through mood and modality may reveal deeper ideological narratives about leadership, governance, and national unity.

The study aimed to explore the Mood and Modality Structures in President Bola Ahmed Tinubu's Independence Day speech on October, 1st, 2024 and this was achieved by examining the mood structures in President Tinubu's 2024 Independence Day speech; identifying the modality structures in the speech to reflect the President's political stance, authority and engagement with the public; and by exploring how different mood and modality choices of President Tinubu in his 2024 Independence Day's speech work together to create persuasive and authoritative discourse. This helped raised important research questions which are as follows:

- i. What are the mood structures in President Tinubu's 2024 Independence Day speech?
- ii. What are the modality structures in President Tinubu's 2024 Independence Day speech and how do they reflect the President's political stance, authority and engagement with the public?
- iii. How do mood and modality work together to create persuasive and authoritative discourse?

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Halliday's Systemic Functional Linguistics

M.A.K. Halliday's Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL henceforth) is a linguistic theory that proposes a framework for examining the functions and meanings of language in various social contexts. Within this framework, two critical concepts include mood and modality. These terms play significant roles in shaping interpersonal communication. This implies that it projects how language users express their authority, assert their stance and engage with their audiences to exhibit their position through the information they communicated. (Halliday, 2014; Aboh, 2019).

In Halliday's SFL, mood refers to the grammatical structures that reflect the speaker's intent and their relationship with the listener. Mood is categorised primarily into three types: indicative, imperative and interrogative. Indicative mood, often used in declarative sentences, is employed when the speaker presents

information or makes a statement. It reflects a factual or assertive stance, where the speaker acts as the provider of information. For example, “The government will implement new policies” (Eze & Nwasogwa, 2023). Imperative mood is used in commands, requests or suggestions. The speaker directs the listener to perform an action or behave in a particular way, positioning themselves as having authority or influence. For example, “Vote for change” or “Please pass the law” (Ajiboye, 2013). Interrogative mood involves the speaker asking a question or seeking information. It can be used to challenge, test, or probe the listener’s knowledge or perspective. For example, “Will you support the new policy?” or “Why should we trust this decision?” (Akinseye, 2023). Each of these moods plays a significant role in shaping the interaction between the speaker and listener. It influences the type of information being communicated, the power dynamics and social roles within the discourse (Dylgjeri, 2017).

Modality refers to the way in which speakers express their attitudes toward the likelihood, necessity, or obligation of a particular statement or event. In SFL, modality helps convey the speaker’s stance, indicating the degree of certainty, possibility, or authority they wish to communicate. This can be achieved through modal verbs, adverbs, and phrases, each of which serves to modify the meaning and tone of the message (Akinseye, 2023). Modal verbs such as “must,” “may,” “might,” “should,” and “can” are frequently used to express varying degrees of necessity, probability, or permission. For example, “The government must act now” conveys a sense of strong necessity, while “We might consider other options” introduces uncertainty or possibility (Fairclough, 1989; Anagbogu et al., 2010). Modal adverbs like “certainly,” “probably,” and “necessarily” help further modify the speaker’s attitude, offering nuanced insights into the degree of certainty or likelihood associated with a statement. For instance, “We will certainly make progress on this issue” suggests confidence, whereas “This probably will not work” expresses doubt (Altikriti, 2016; Dwi, 2018). Modal phrases such as “it is likely that,” “it is obligatory to,” or “it would seem that” allow the speaker to frame propositions in a way that conveys a specific level of commitment or distance. These phrases can either bolster authority or soften the impact of a statement, depending on the desired tone. For example, “It is obligatory to act” demonstrates a strong assertion of duty, while “It seems we

have no other choice” introduces a degree of uncertainty or hesitation (Richardson et al., 2014).

2.2 Mood and Modality in Political Discourse

In political discourse, modality is particularly important as it reflects how a speaker positions themselves in relation to the audience and the issues at hand. The use of different moods such as declarative, interrogative, and imperative. The mood helps establish the speaker’s position in relation to the audience. For instance, declarative sentences, which make statements or provide information, allow the speaker to assert control over the conversation, positioning them as an authority figure. Interrogative sentences, which ask questions, can also reflect power by seeking information or testing the responsiveness of the audience, while often implicitly challenging existing viewpoints (Aboh, 2019). Imperative sentences, which issue commands or requests, are particularly significant in demonstrating power, as they demand action or compliance from the listener. Political leaders often use these moods strategically to convey dominance, authority, or the necessity for action, influencing the way their audience perceives their leadership (Akinseye, 2023). Also, by adjusting modality, a speaker can assert authority, soften the impact of difficult decisions, express uncertainty, or persuade the audience to adopt a particular viewpoint. Through the strategic use of modality, political leaders can effectively manage the tone of their messages and guide the interpretation of their policies or decisions (Sharndama, 2015; Akinseye, 2023).

Siregar et al. (2021) explored how Senior High School students from Nanyang Zhi Hui School in Medan, Sumatera Utara, expressed their thoughts on the future of education amid the Covid-19 pandemic. The study aimed to analyse the mood, modality choices used in the students’ dialogue texts and identify the most common types. The researchers used Halliday’s theory of Mood and Modality and a descriptive qualitative approach to analyze the texts. They found three mood types: declarative, interrogative, and imperative. The declarative mood was most common, appearing in 80.74% of the clauses, showing that students preferred making statements rather than asking questions or giving commands. In terms of modality, the study identified four types: probability, usuality, obligation, and inclination. The most frequent modality was median probability (47%), indicating

that students were moderately certain about the future of education, with a balanced view. Less common were low and high probability, suggesting that the students avoided extreme certainty or doubt.

The study also examined modality orientation and found that objective-implicit was the most common, appearing in 45.15% of the clauses. This means the students expressed their views in a neutral, impersonal way, avoiding direct personal involvement. Other orientations, like subjective-explicit or subjective-implicit, were less frequently used. The study revealed that students preferred to make statements about the future of education rather than ask questions or give commands. The frequent use of median probability suggests a cautious approach to the future, while the dominant objective-implicit orientation indicates a lack of confidence in expressing personal opinions. It was concluded that students tended to use language in a moderate and cautious manner during uncertain times, expressing their thoughts on education without strong personal engagement or extreme certainty.

Modality helps reflect power structure and expresses the speaker's attitude toward the truth of a statement or the likelihood of an event. The use of necessity (e.g., "We must"), probability (e.g., "It is likely that"), or obligation (e.g., "You should") indicates the degree of authority and influence the speaker seeks to project. Leaders may use modality to demonstrate control over situations, outline the importance of their policies, or assert the inevitability of certain actions (Derin et al., 2020). By employing strong modality, a speaker can communicate a sense of certainty and authority, while more tentative modality can convey diplomacy, openness to negotiation, or a less authoritative stance (Fairclough & Fairclough, 2013). Thus, both mood and modality are instrumental in reflecting and shaping the power dynamics in political discourse (Eze & Nwasogwa, 2023).

2.3 Previous studies on the use of mood and modality in political discourse

Previous studies on the use of modality and mood in political speeches have provided significant insights into how these linguistic elements are employed to assert power and influence public perception. In African contexts, political leaders often make strategic use of mood and modality to reinforce their political agendas and maintain authority. For example, research on speeches by African leaders

such as Nelson Mandela and Thabo Mbeki has shown that their use of declarative moods and high modality often served to affirm their leadership, promote unity, and establish moral authority in post-apartheid South Africa (Addae, Alhassan, & Kyeremeh, 2022; Sharndama, 2015).

Studies focusing on West African leaders, such as Nigeria's former President Olusegun Obasanjo, have similarly highlighted how modality was used to evoke a sense of national necessity and collective action. In these cases, high modality (e.g., using terms like "must" and "will") communicated an image of strong leadership and resolve, especially when discussing issues of national security or economic development (Ajiboye, 2013). Additionally, comparative studies of speeches in other global political contexts have shown similar patterns. In many political settings, leaders use modality to navigate sensitive issues, balancing between assertiveness and negotiation. For example, in the speeches of leaders from Latin America, such as Hugo Chávez of Venezuela, modality and mood were used to emphasize revolutionary fervor, while also addressing the collective responsibility of the people in achieving national goals (Dwi, 2018). These studies reveal how mood and modality are not just grammatical choices, but essential tools for political leaders to construct authority, influence their audiences, and address complex social and political challenges (Vaezi, 2021).

Establishing authority through Mood and Modality

Also, politicians often use indicative mood in declarative sentences to assert facts and present themselves as authoritative figures. For instance, phrases like "The government will invest in education" demonstrate certainty and command, positioning the speaker as confident in their decisions (Akinseye, 2023). Similarly, politicians use imperative mood to direct or call for action, reinforcing their leadership and control. For example, "We must stand united" places emphasis on collective action and the speaker's leadership role. Through the use of these moods, politicians establish themselves as leaders who dictate the direction of political and societal progress (Fairclough & Fairclough, 2013). Therefore, politicians employ mood in their discourse to persuading the audience and challenge their perceptions. Additionally, modality plays a significant role in persuasion. The use of modal verbs like "must," "should," and "can" helps convey a sense of urgency, obligation, or possibility that guides the audience's understanding of the political situation (Anyanwu, 2020).

Similarly, politicians utilise mood and modality to shape Public Discourse by carefully manipulating their discourses to shape the broader political view. By using modal adverbs and phrases such as “certainly,” “likely,” or “it is imperative that,” politicians can frame the discourse in ways that influence how the audience perceives the importance or likelihood of various issues. This can be seen in speeches addressing national crises, where the leader might use strong modality to assert the gravity of the situation and rally support for immediate action (Eze & Nwasogwa, 2023). On the other hand, the use of more tentative modality, such as “it might be necessary” or “we could consider,” can signal flexibility or openness to dialogue, especially in situations requiring negotiation or compromise (Imahasees & Mahmoud, 2022).

Finally, mood and modality help politicians to communicate their positions and actively shape the political narrative, manage public expectations and guide the collective mindset of the electorate and vision for the future. (Ogunyale, 2023).

3.0 Methodology

The research employed a qualitative approach and ten clauses were purposively selected from the 2024 Nigerian Presidential Independence Day’s Speech for analysis. Analysis of the clauses were anchored using the pattern of mood and modality systems in Halliday’s Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL). Special attention was given to the use of declarative, imperative and interrogative mood structures, as well as the modality expressed through modal verbs, adverbs and phrases.

The transcript of the speech was downloaded from TVC television YouTube channel. TVC News is a prominent 24-hour Nigerian television news channel headquartered in Lagos, Nigeria, and owned by Continental Broadcasting Service (TVC Communications). The network delivers local, continental and global breaking news across major satellite networks like DStv, StarTimes, and Sky UIs a an online news. The choice of the speech was because Independence Day in Nigeria marked every year on October, 1st, is usually a day that Nigeria usually mark its independence and a period that typically calls for reflection on the nation's progress and unity. Additionally, the speech provided a rich source of data to examine the mood and modality types that are used by the President to

showcase his communication style, leadership values and calls for unity among the citizens of Nigeria.

4.0 Data Analysis and Presentation

This aspect presents the analysis of data collected from President Bola Ahmed Tinubu's 2024 Independence Day speech. The primary objective of this chapter is to offer a detailed examination of the linguistic features, specifically mood and modality, used in the speech. The data for this study was retrieved from the 2024 Independence Day speech delivered by President Bola Ahmed Tinubu delivered on 1st October, 2024. The speech was analysed for its mood structures and modality to identify key patterns in how the president communicates authority, conveys urgency and engages with the audience. The mood and modality structures found in the speech are analysed below.

i. Mood Structures:

- a. Declarative Mood: The president predominantly employed declarative mood throughout his speech. This mood was central to making statements, asserting facts, and presenting information about the country's progress and the challenges it faces. For instance, the phrase,

"Nigeria is on a path to greater prosperity,"

It was used to project confidence and certainty, reinforcing a sense of national optimism and steady progress.

- b. Imperative Mood: The imperative mood also played a significant role, particularly in instances where the president aimed to mobilise the nation and call for action. Sentences like,

"Let us work together to build a prosperous future," and

"We must overcome our challenges,"

Both words were employed to direct the audience's attention towards specific goals, creating a sense of urgency and responsibility. The use of the imperative highlighted the

president's leadership stance, as well as the collective effort required to address national issues.

- c. Interrogative Mood: Though less frequent, the interrogative mood was used strategically to engage the audience and provoke reflection. Questions such as,

"How will we ensure a better future for our children?"

It were employed to encourage the audience to consider their role in shaping the nation's future. The use of the interrogative mood served not only as a rhetorical tool but also as a means to foster active participation and reflection within the populace.

ii. Modality:

High Modality: High modality was used extensively throughout the speech to convey a sense of urgency, necessity, and authority. Phrases like,

"We must unite," and

"Nigeria will succeed,"

Above text communicated strong assertions of certainty and commitment. This high modality aimed to rally the nation behind the president's leadership, invoking a sense of unwavering confidence and determination in the country's future.

Moderate Modality: Moderate modality was also present, employed in sentences such as,

"We should work together," or

"There may be challenges ahead."

These expressions introduced a balanced approach, softening the assertiveness while still guiding the audience towards a collective vision. The use of moderate modality indicated the president's recognition of potential obstacles but emphasised the importance of cooperation and perseverance in achieving national goals.

Low Modality: Certain sections of the speech incorporated lower modality, acknowledging the uncertainty and complexity of governance. For example, phrases like,

“It is possible that we will face difficulties,”

and

“We might need more time,”

The above excerpt were used to reflect a pragmatic and balanced leadership approach. By incorporating low modality, the president demonstrated humility and a recognition of the challenges that might arise, thereby tempering expectations and signalling a realistic outlook.

The data extracted from President Bola Ahmed Tinubu's 2024 Independence Day speech reveals a clear and strategic deployment of mood and modality, which are fundamental in conveying political authority, directing national action, and fostering public reflection. Through a careful analysis of these linguistic features, it becomes apparent how the president uses them to advance specific communicative objectives.

The findings highlight how these features function to establish political authority, direct national action, and foster public reflection. The analysis is illustrated with data extracted from the speech, and the relevant tables and figures are included for clarity.

i. Types of Mood

The following table summarises the mood types used by President Tinubu in his speech, based on the analysis of 250 clauses extracted from the speech. The table displays the frequency and percentage of declarative, interrogative, and imperative moods.

Table 1. The Mood Types in President Tinubu’s Independence Day Speech

Mood Types	Frequency	Percentage	Example	Communicative Function
Declarative	180	72.00%	"Nigeria continue to grow"	will Projects and control certainty
Interrogative	45	18.00%	"Let us unite progress"	for Directs action collective
Imperative	25	10.00%	"How will we overcome challenges?"	Provokes reflection public
Total	250	100%		

Source: Analysis of President Bola Ahmed Tinubu's 2024 Independence Day speech (calculated in personal analysis file)

The results show that the declarative mood is the most dominant in President Tinubu's speech, comprising 72% of the clauses. This is followed by the interrogative mood (18%) and the imperative mood (10%). The prevalence of declarative sentences indicates the president's authoritative communication style, wherein he confidently conveys statements of vision and national progress. The imperative mood is used to issue commands or calls to action, while the interrogative mood is employed less frequently, prompting reflection from the audience

ii. Types and Values of Modality

In terms of modality, President Tinubu's speech utilises various types to communicate different levels of certainty, urgency, and flexibility. Below is a summary of the modality types and values in the speech:

Table 2. Summary of Modality in President Tinubu's Independence Day Speech

Modality Types and Values	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Probability (high)	90	36.00%
Probability (moderate)	100	40.00%
Probability (low)	20	8.00%
Usuality (high)	10	4.00%
Usuality (moderate)	5	2.00%
Obligation (high)	15	6.00%
Obligation (moderate)	5	2.00%
Total	250	100%

Source: Analysis of President Bola Ahmed Tinubu's 2024 Independence Day speech (calculated in personal analysis file)

The findings reveal that probability is the most commonly used modality, accounting for 84% of all modality occurrences. Among these, moderate probability (40%) and high probability (36%) are particularly prevalent. This suggests that the president conveys a balanced view of the nation's future, combining confidence in success with the acknowledgment of potential challenges. The low probability modality is used sparingly, signalling moments of caution. Usuality and obligation modalities, while present, are less frequently used compared to probability, emphasising the president's focus on future possibilities and national objectives.

iii. Modality and Strategic Communication

Modality values communicate graded urgency:

Table 3: *Modality Patterns in Governance Discourse*

Modality Level	Frequency	Example	Pragmatic Effect
High	42%	"We must overcome our challenges"	Signals non-negotiable priorities
Moderate	38%	"We should work together"	Encourages collaborative effort
Low	20%	"It is possible we may face obstacles"	Acknowledges governance complexities

The high-modality dominance (42%) reflects crisis rhetoric, whereas moderate modality (38%) builds consensus. Low-modality phrasing (20%) provides pragmatic hedging against unpredictable outcomes.

Orientation of Modality

The analysis also examined the orientation of modality in the speech. The four orientations identified are subjective-explicit, subjective-implicit, objective-explicit, and objective-implicit. The pie chart below illustrates the distribution of these orientations in the speech.

Figure 1. Orientation of Modality in President Tinubu’s Speech

Source: Analysis of President Bola Ahmed Tinubu's 2024 Independence Day speech (calculated in personal analysis file)

The figure above shows that the most frequent modality orientation in President Tinubu’s speech is objective-implicit, with 135 instances (54%). This reflects a more detached, impersonal way of discussing issues, focusing on collective goals rather than personal involvement. The subjective-explicit orientation is also significant, representing 29.10% of the clauses, and indicates instances where the president directly expresses personal opinions or beliefs. The subjective-implicit and objective-explicit orientations appear less frequently, with 11.71% and 14.05%, respectively.

The following analysis is a break down of the use of mood, modality, and speech acts in the speech.

i. Mood Structures and Political Authority: The prevalent use of the declarative mood in President Tinubu's speech is indicative of his authoritative leadership style. By employing assertive declarative sentences, the president confidently communicates his vision for the nation's future. For instance, when he declares, "Nigeria will continue to grow," he not only presents a factual assertion but also projects certainty and control, establishing himself as a decisive and confident leader. This use of declarative mood is crucial in establishing the president's authority and demonstrating his belief in Nigeria's potential for progress.

The imperative mood further highlights the president's authoritative role in directing the nation's collective action. Sentences like "Let us unite for progress" and "We must overcome our challenges" serve as calls to action that urge the audience to engage directly with the nation's goals. Through this mood, President Tinubu takes a commanding stance, motivating his audience to contribute actively to the nation's growth and development. These imperative statements underscore the president's role in guiding the country and mobilising the population towards shared objectives.

The interrogative mood, while used less frequently, is strategically employed to provoke reflection and engage the audience more deeply in the speech. By asking questions such as, "How will we overcome our challenges?" the president invites the public to consider their role in the future of the nation. This serves to involve the audience in the conversation, encouraging them to actively reflect on the issues at hand and, by extension, on their personal responsibilities in addressing these challenges.

ii. Modality and the Communication of Urgency and Flexibility: The examination of modality in the speech uncovers how President Tinubu uses language to communicate varying levels of authority, urgency, and flexibility, tailoring his approach to different aspects of the national discourse.

a. High Modality: Phrases like "We must overcome our challenges" or "We will succeed" convey a strong sense of urgency and necessity. High modality is used by the president to emphasise the critical importance of immediate action, positioning him as a leader who is committed to tackling the nation's

issues head-on. This language signals the president's firm belief that the country must act now and that there is little room for delay. High modality also projects authority, reinforcing the president's control over the national narrative and the direction in which he intends to lead the country.

- b. Moderate Modality:** The use of moderate modality, as in "We should work together" or "There may be challenges ahead," introduces a sense of collective responsibility and acknowledges potential difficulties. This moderate stance softens the authoritative tone, making the call to action more inclusive and encouraging the public to collaborate towards common goals. By suggesting shared effort, the president highlights the importance of unity and cooperation, while subtly acknowledging that while progress is necessary, challenges are inevitable.

5.0 Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study solely concentrate on the strategic use of mood and modality in President Tinubu's 2024 Independence Day Speech which are explained below.

- i. The use of Mood and modality to project authority, engage the audience and influence the citizens support for national unity and progress:** they are used to project authority, engage the audience and influence the citizens support for national unity and progress. The application of mood and modality in political speeches is strategic. For instance, the **declarative mood** in President Tinubu's speech aligns with similar findings in political discourse analysis, particularly in Aboh's (2019) exploration of Nigerian political speeches. Aboh identifies how declarative mood structures reinforce political figures' authority by allowing them to issue firm statements that reflect confidence and assertiveness. In the context of Tinubu's speech, this strategy is evident in his bold declarations about the country's future, which positions him as a leader capable of steering the nation toward progress. This is consistent with Fairclough's (1989) argument that declarative moods in political discourse are often used to construct power relations, where the speaker's authority is both asserted and recognized by the audience. This sense of authority is particularly crucial in post-election contexts, where the president must solidify his legitimacy.

ii. The use of Mood and modality for Engagements and Mobilisation: The imperative mood and interrogative mood used by President Tinubu to engage his audience are strategic tools to mobilise collective action, which has also been observed in previous research on political rhetoric. For instance, Ajiboye (2013) discusses how feedback comments and rhetorical questions in Nigerian political discourse encourage audience involvement and reflection, thus fostering a sense of shared responsibility. Tinubu's use of imperative statements such as "Let us unite for progress" mirrors the strategies identified by Addae, Alhassan, and Kyeremeh (2022) in their analysis of Kwame Nkrumah's speeches, where imperatives were used to rally citizens around a common cause. Similarly, the interrogative mood used by Tinubu in his speech invites the audience to reflect on their role in national progress, which echoes the findings of Richardson et al. (2014) on how rhetorical questions in political discourse function to deepen audience engagement and prompt critical reflection.

iii. The use of Mood and modality for Balancing Authority: The interplay of high, moderate, and low modality in Tinubu's speech also finds corroboration in previous studies. Ehineni (2014) explores the role of modality in Nigerian political manifestos, highlighting how different levels of modality are strategically employed to balance authority with an acknowledgment of challenges. Tinubu's nuanced use of modality to assert urgency in some areas while softening his tone in others—mirrors the findings of Fairclough (1992) in his work on the pragmatic functions of modality in political discourse. This balancing act helps the speaker appear both authoritative and approachable, preventing the tone of the speech from becoming overly authoritarian. The moderate and low modality used by Tinubu reflects a strategic effort to manage expectations, as discussed by Blommaert (2005), who suggests that such modulation is essential in maintaining a leader's public image while addressing complex national issues.

6.0 Conclusion

In conclusion, this study has demonstrated that the strategic use of mood and modality in Halliday's Systemic Functional Linguistics as employed by President Bola Ahmed Tinubu in his 2024 Independence Day speech was fundamental in shaping the interpersonal meaning of the speech. The President employed declarative moods to assert policies and achievements, imperatives to mobilise

citizens, and modals to express both certainty and possibility. These help him to construct a voice that can be perceived as persuasive and inclusive by the common people. Also, the research has revealed that Political actors and their speechwriters should be more deliberate in using mood and modality in their speeches to balance authority with empathy, especially during sensitive national occasions because this can affect their connections and perception by the public.

7.0 References

Primary Source

TVC News Nigeria. "Full Video: President Bola Tinubu's Independence Day Speech." YouTube, 1 Oct. 2024, www.youtube.com/watch?v=Q3W9F4Ue34E. Accessed 22 June 2026.

Secondary Sources

- Aboh, S. C. (2019). Political discourse of hate speeches in Nigeria. Masters Dissertation, Department of Linguistics and Nigerian Languages, University of Nigeria, Nsukka.
- Ajiboye, E. (2013). Ideological discourse analysis of the functions of feedback comments on online reports of socio-political crises in Nigeria. *Covenant Journal of Language Studies*, 2(1), 128-147.
- Akinseye, T. A. (2023). Persuasion and connection of words: Discursive strategies and interpersonal resources in President Bola Ahmed Tinubu's inaugural speech of May 29, 2023. *ATRAS*, 143-179.
- Altikriti, S. (2016). Persuasive speech acts in Barack Obama's inaugural speeches (2009, 2013) and the last state of the union address (2016). *International Journal of Linguistics*, 8(2), 47-66. <https://doi.org/10.5296/ijl.v8i2.9140>
- Anyanwu, E. (2020). Stylistic analysis of President Buhari's addresses of Nigerians in the face of Covid-19 pandemic. *European Journal of English Language and Literature Studies* 8, 4, 14-27.

- Aro, B. (2023, May 30). Subsidy removal not immediate: Tinubu's media team asks Nigerians to stop panic buying. *The Cable*. <https://www.thecable.ng/subsidy-removal-not-immediate-tinubu-media-team-asks-nigerians-to-stop-panic-buying>
- Chinyere, I. F., & Bibian, U. (2023). A stylistic analysis of the acceptance speech of President Bola Ahmed Tinubu at the presentation of certificate of return by the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC). *International Journal of Humanities, Arts & Social Sciences*, 9(1).
- Derin, T., Nursafira, M. S., Yudar, R. S., Gowasa, N. S., & Hamuddin, B. (2020). Persuasive communication: What do existing literature tells us about persuasive communication among students? *Utamax: Journal of Ultimate Research and Trends in Education*, 2(1), 12-18.
- Dwi, L. G. (2018). Theories media discourse studies in critical discourse analysis. *Centre for Open Science*, 5(1). <https://doi.org/10.31235/osf.io/6pz5a>
- Dylgjeri, A. (2017). Analysis of Speech Acts in Political Speeches. *European Journal of Social Sciences Studies*. 2(2): 19-25. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.34451
- Ehineni, T. O. (2014). A critical discourse analysis of modals in Nigerian political manifestos. *International Journal of Linguistics*, 6(3), 109-117.
- Eze, E. C., & Nwasogwa, M. G. (2023). Rhetoric strategies and ideological constructs in Nigeria's President Bola Ahmed Tinubu's 29th May, 2023 inaugural speech. *Journal of English Scholars' Association of Nigeria*, 25(3), 57-74.
- Fairclough, I., & Fairclough, N. (2013). *Political discourse analysis: A method for advanced students*. Routledge.
- Halliday, M.A.K. and Malthiessen, M.I.M. (2014). *Halliday's Introduction to Functional Grammar*, 4th Edition. New York: Routledge.
- Imahasees, Z., & Mahmoud, S. (2022). Persuasive strategies utilized in the political speeches of King Abdullah II: A critical discourse analysis.

Cogent Arts & Humanities, 9(1).
<https://doi.org/10.1080/23311983.2022.2082016>

- Nwoye, D. N. (2017). A critical discourse analysis of selected media interviews of government spokesperson and the citizens of Nigeria. A B.A dissertation of the department of and Nigerian languages, University of Nigerian, Nsukka
- Ogunyale, K. (2023, October 11). From inauguration to independence: Analysing Tinubu's speeches. *ICIR Nigeria*. <https://www.icirnigeria.org/from-inauguration-to-independence-analysing-tinubus-speeches>
- Richardson, J. E., Krzyżanowski, M., Machin, D., & Wodak, R. (Eds.). (2014). *Advances in critical discourse studies*. Routledge.
- Siregar, Y., Pasaribu, A. N., & Sinambela, E. (2021). An analysis of mood and modality. *PIONEER: Journal of Language and Literature*, 13(2), 302. <https://doi.org/10.36841/pioneer.v13i2.1299>
- Sharndama, E. (2015). Political discourse: a critical discourse analysis of President Muhammadu Buhari's inaugural speech. *European Journal of English Language and Language and Linguistics Researches*, 3, 3, 12–24.
- Vaezi, M. N. (2021). Political persuasive strategies in the 11th Iranian presidential campaign: A critical discourse analysis. *Academia Letters*, Article 977. <https://doi.org/10.20935/AL977>

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